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A Historical Analysis of the Impacts of US-India Defense Collaboration over the South Asian Regional Political Dynamics

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ABSTRACT

The defense cooperation between the United States (US) and India undertaken primarily in the backdrop of the War Against Terrorism empowered India to boost its defensive capabilities up to such an extent that it could threaten the regional peace which ultimately happened at the end of the second decade of the 21st century when deadly Indian military aggression surfaced practically against Pakistan and China in 2019-20 with the unfortunate exception that the episode against Pakistan was repeated in May 2025 nevertheless all these violent military attacks were successfully defeated by the rival armies while leaving the impact that India had continuously been endangering the regional peace. Although these developments had been prematurely sensed and the regional security circles were pointing out that the US should not provide modern arms and weaponry to the Indian military so that it might avoid involving in direct clashes with the neighboring states but none paid any heed to such sane voices. Moving upon this background, the current study reviews the India-US defense collaboration in historical perspective to assess and understand that how the same had resulted in polluting the South Asian regional peace? It finds that although the US presence in Afghanistan was a major factor for the US search for a trustworthy regional ally nevertheless it was the China's

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economic progress by leaps and bounds which forced the US to modernize the Indian defensive and attacking capabilities so that the US hegemonic designs pertaining to the region could not be disturbed. However, the cooperation also brought negative consequences as well since both China and Pakistan came strategically further closer which resulted in the humiliating defeat of Indian army time and again. The study recommends that US defense establishment should maintain a rationally designed and balanced approach while adopting any arms supply mechanism to the South Asian states so that the balance of power might not swing in favor of any one state.

Key Words: US-India Defense Cooperation, Pakistan-China relations, Nuclear Proliferation, CPEC

1. Introduction

The signing of India-US Civil Nuclear Agreement in 2005 marked a significant milestone in the bilateral relationship of both countries. Despite not possessing the membership of the Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty (NPT), the arrangement blessed India with the exceptional ability to obtain civilian nuclear technology from the US and other nuclear powers hence the agreement brought an end to long prevailed distrust since the times of Cold War and a new era of collaboration begun which was founded on jointly shared interests of both countries in terms of prevention of security threats and curtailing the growth of China's power around the world. Afterwards, the U.S.-India relationship turned further stronger during 2014 after Mr. Narendra Modi took office of the Prime Minister of India who strongly believed in strengthening the India-US relations especially in the fields of defense, commercial connections, and strategic collaboration while particularly focusing over the Asia-Pacific region. As both countries were concerned about China's continuously increasing power in the world in general and in the region in particular, Mr. Modi characterized his foreign policy objectives as "Act East" along with "Free and Open Indo-Pacific" doctrines which also were in line with American foreign policy objectives with respect to the concerned region. It goes without saying that, given the conflict between India and Pakistan, the Indo-U.S. strategic partnership had been posing a greater threat to the latter. Although Pakistan faced numerous difficulties and concerns related to terrorism, India posed the greatest challenge to

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Pakistan, hence Pakistan's attention was mostly focused on India (Bukhari, 2011).

India changed its foreign policy and started working more closely with the US after the US emerged as the most powerful actor in the globe. In response, the US helped India achieve its goal of becoming a South Asian Great Power. Power gaps in South Asia could be made worse by the strategic relationship among the United States as well as India. The Indo-US strategic partnership was largely the result of strong anti-American sentiments which were present in the civil society and body politic of Pakistan.

The security situation and environment of the entire region, especially for Pakistan, had adversely been impacted by the strategic relationship among the US and India in the field of missile defense systems (Amin, 2021).

2. Nuclear Collaboration

The Indo-US defense cooperation had the potential to upset the balance of power in the region between India and Pakistan, the two fierce competitors, from a strategic perspective. The United States, officially a nuclear power, was believed to be working with India on matters related to nuclear energy. In addition to undermining article 1 of the NPT, which declared that nuclear weapon states would not provide aid to non-nuclear states in obtaining nuclear capabilities, the collaboration put questions over the fundamental principles of the NPT. The NPT's foundation did not support India's nuclearization in spite of the fact that it was an officially proclaimed nuclear weapon state. Because each signing state of the NPT, being a party to the NPT, had pledged not to transfer nuclear material or nuclear devices and not to encourage or help any state that was a non-nuclear weapon state under the NPT to produce nuclear weapons, the US-India cooperation was undermining the NPT's basic principles and articles (Bukhari, 2011).

The nuclear accord among the US and India was considered a matter of civil jurisdiction merely through the courtesy of its name. It was executed in such manner just to reduce any concerns that could arise from the agreement since it was not practicable for the United States to redirect civil nuclear technology provided to India for military use. India's use of civil nuclear power for defense purposes was a threat resulting from the civil nuclear pact. The agreement also stated that India was free to purchase traditional arms from the US at any time, and they undoubtedly

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did so. Such actions/agreements ultimately had to escalate the hostility between India and Pakistan and upset the balance of power among the two nations soon after they were put into effect. That development also made it more difficult to resolve the long-standing disputes between the two nations, especially pertaining to the water and Kashmir issues. Because of India-Pakistan rivalry, the Indo-US nuclear partnership intensified an arms race between the two nuclear powers, which consequently led to war anxiety in South Asia. Alongside that, an arms race in a region where China, India, and Pakistan held nuclear weapons could put the global peace and security at risk (Kirk, 2008).

India was utilizing its strategic cooperation with the US to counterbalance China's dominance in the Indo-Pacific, which was changing the structure of the region. India's fiscal and military abilities were strengthened by its strong links with a major power such as the US, which raised its geostrategic standing and firmly established it as a major regional actor. Furthermore, that alliance supported a common goal of preserving the balance of power and strengthened the US's strategic position in Asia. However, Pakistan faced serious difficulties as a result of that collaboration (Amir, 2024).

3. Economic Impacts of US-India Strategic Relations

The already solid Indian economy gained a great lot from the defense agreement with the United States. In addition to professional exchanges in all fields and developmental initiatives, it opened the door to a solid corporate relationship not only between the US and India but for their allies as well. In fact, the US benefited more from this as the US production businesses now had a bigger market to sell their goods in. This agreement created doors for commerce in several industries in addition to facilitating the interchange of military weapons. In order to support its economy and establish a strong presence in its client nations, India started selling US goods at extremely low prices on behalf of the US as the two nations got closer. Besides, Pakistan was denied access to US technology and the US preferred to sell its goods to India, which further extended the distance between the arch-rivals. Pakistan thus remained far behind to India in terms of technological developments to support its economy (Pant & Super, 2015). Accordingly, it was clear that the collaborative China-Pakistan geopolitical and development initiatives reflected the

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impact of strategic partnership between the United States and India. India's growing aspirations to get somewhat sophisticated nuclear weapons were upsetting the nuclear visions and strategies followed by Beijing and Islamabad. China and Pakistan both viewed their nuclear installations endangered because of Indian intentions of seeking US patronage and assistance (Jain, 2016).

It might be safely observed that the shift of Pakistan's foreign policy towards the East was the ultimate result of the growing relations between the US and India. Because of the swiftly-changing geo-strategic and political landscape of South Asian region particularly owing to the US alignment with India and the probable alienation of Pakistan caused by the said alignment, Pakistan was forced to look for other diplomatic options while particularly focusing over China. In other words, Pakistan leant towards China and Russia in order to offset the challenges caused by the strategic alliance between the US and India. Enhancing relations with these countries could offer a more suitable alternative for Pakistan in the geostrategic perspective and fulfil its economic requirements while keeping a lesser reliance over the United States. In order to avoid bearing the weight of the US-India relationship alone, Pakistan made efforts to foster friendly relations with the other neighboring and regional countries. It was commonly perceived in Pakistan that, in order to challenge India's authoritarian approach, Pakistan must have to alter its foreign policy and link itself strategically with other nations since the US-India cooperation was founded on principles of mutual interests. Under the cover of a growing strategic cooperation with the US, India's primary goal was to contain Pakistan and China and their growing influence over South Asian political dynamics. Since Pakistan had serious concerns as regard to US-India partnership hence it examined the nature of its relationship with the United States and came up with an alternate plan and strategy to strengthen its ties with the eastern nations. One notable example of that alternate strategy was the growing relationship and strategic cooperation between China and Pakistan. Pakistan changed its foreign policy, which was already leaning toward China, in order to preserve the strategic balance of power in the region. That was because, during the end-phase of the Cold War, Pakistan's ties with the US began to deteriorate and the US ties started improving in the case of India. China had already been Pakistan's all-weather friend since the

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beginning, and as a result of this strategic alliance, Pakistan started depending more on China because China continued to support Pakistan in all discussion boards whether held at domestic or foreign level. Given Pakistan's tense relations with India, the collaboration between India and the US had become even more crucial (Kumar, 2014).

4. Strategic Impacts for Pakistan

Pakistan's security had clearly and significantly been impacted adversely by the US strategic alliance with India. Furthermore, India's hostile attitude toward Pakistan was encouraged by US political and military assistance whereas Pakistan's access to the latest technology had been severely and discriminatorily restricted by the United States, by applying both official and unofficial means. There had also been pressure on China to stay away from providing Pakistan access to weapons and innovative technologies. It was feared that Pakistan's conventional defense and nuclear arms structure would be significantly impacted in the absence of modern upgradation and supportive mechanisms (Iqbal,2020). According to the interviews of some security officers, India might target Pakistan's border regions for conducting false flag operations, particularly Gilgit-Baltistan (GB) and Azad Jammu and Kashmir (AJK). Because of its advanced monitoring and reconnaissance capabilities, India could now more efficiently target and monitor places in these regions with the help of US technology. The sources feared that the future conflicts might threaten the security and stability of these regions due to India's growing military push. However, as China was also a significant player in the region, India's attempts to bring in the GB region into the Kashmir dispute could not succeed. Given that China and Pakistan had both demonstrated their strength against India in the Balakot and Galwan Heights crises in 2019 and 2020, respectively, it was generally believed that the least desirable option for Indian military planners to simultaneously confront with both countries. The likelihood of India-Pakistan cross-border hostilities and clashes particularly along the Line of Control (LoC) and their International Border was increased by India's improved military capabilities under the US patronage. Pakistan's strategic operations and capabilities were seriously threatened by India's increased Intelligence, Surveillance, and Reconnaissance (ISR) capabilities, which were supported by US technology. Because of the greater operational capabilities

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and readiness of the Indian armed forces, Pakistan's military was forced to proportionately maintain a high level of alertness and readiness. Pakistan's operational capability and military resources were further challenged by that ongoing pressure. The potential for errors of judgment, unintentional management, and conflict further complicated the security issues in such tight settings (Khan, 2024).

Since 97% of Pakistan's trade depended on the sea, Pakistan risked serious implications owing to the increasing US-India strategic ties. Gwadar port currently handled the majority of Pakistan's maritime traffic. Additionally, the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) enhanced Pakistan's economic capabilities. Pakistan's marine commerce was under a threat if India placed a prohibition on shipping routes. Oceanic routes and marine commerce were also essential to China and other regional governments. About 60% of the United States' naval forces had been placed in the ocean, especially in the region of the Malacca Strait. The relationship between regional and international stakeholders would be complicated and would result in military and economic crisis if any powerful force enforced a blockade in the region (Tahir & Ejaz, 2020).

The goals of Indo-US missile defense cooperation had been summed up in the Trump administration's 2019-Missile Defense Review as follows: "The risks presented by offensive missile abilities are no longer confined to a few areas within the world. There are presently a number of states in South Asia that are establishing a progressed and different range of ballistic and cruise missile capabilities." In that setting, the US talked about possible missile defense collaboration with India, which was a logical progression of India's position as a Major Defense Partner and an essential component of the US Indo-Pacific Strategy. Pakistan as a threat to India was not specifically mentioned in the Missile Defense Review report. There was no denying that both nations (India & Pakistan) were engaged in a missile arms race. The Trump administration's focus on talking about possible missile defense collaboration with India to counter missile threats from rivals suggested that the US might assist India in resisting Pakistan's missiles (Saeed & Javaid, 2020).

5. The Counterbalancing Strategies by Pakistan

The increasing cooperation between the two countries had put the regional security

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at danger as the US continued to enhance India's defense abilities. Security in South Asia was already unstable, and it was getting worse due to US defense cooperation and arms transfers to India. The aspirations of India to become a great power and its function as a "net security provider" for the US were increasing the regional instability. Additionally, Pakistan was directly impacted by Indo-US defense collaboration. India's traditional and nuclear arms capabilities were being strengthened thanks to the US assistance. Although India wanted to develop its military capabilities and fulfill its geopolitical goals of becoming a regional hegemon, it was positioning itself as a counterbalancing option/power against China. In addition to promoting regional instability as mentioned, India's geopolitical objectives and ambitions raised questions about its ability to be a trustworthy US ally. The US-led western bloc's enormous tolerance had proved advantageous to India. Supporting India's military expansion was clearly against/contrary to the non-proliferation regime's promises. The US had given access to India in terms of modern military technologies despite India's questionable previous record of proliferation, which raised concerns about the US position as a responsible global power. Additionally, the collaboration between US and India might have major consequences for Pakistan, even though the US Indo-Pacific policy was largely focused on maritime cooperation and sought to strengthen India's marine capabilities against China. Pakistan's security situation also deteriorated as a consequence of US measures to strengthen India's naval capabilities. In addition, the region's arms race grew more intense as a result of India's plans to develop more weapons for its sea-variants of shipment system (Kakar, 2022).

Additionally, Pakistan was affected politically by the personal relationship between Donald Trump and Narendra Modi, the leaders of the United States and India, which helped improving the security and defense relationship between US and India. Furthermore, strategic alliances, planning/support, mutual trade, diplomacy as well as regional politics were all significantly impacted and strengthened by their partnership. Pakistan's military balance and strategic position in South Asia were also negatively affected by this enhanced partnership. The US had supported India's stance on terrorism, particularly with reference to cross-border terrorism that was supposedly coming/infiltrated from Pakistan. Pakistan was diplomatically isolated

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as a result of the closer connection between India and the US since the latter had virtually cut all military and economic aid to Pakistan during the first term of President Trump, claiming that the country was failing to combat terrorism. This action was viewed as a result of the expanding strategic alliance between India and the United States. Pakistan was then highly concerned about its security as a result of increased military cooperation between India and the United States, which was expanding from arms deals to combined military drills and exercises (Shahbaz, 2024). Alongside, the military in Pakistan suffered greatly since the country's economic situation did not improve substantially. Keeping in view the importance of naval boundaries, military exercises and operations in the sea are primarily conducted to monitor enemy forces and their existence in the ocean. India and the United States held extensive naval drills/operations in the Indian Ocean region which were called Malabar exercises. Significant allies of the United States and India were Japan and Australia, and their combined military exercise was referred to as the Quad. In order to overcome the technology-deficit during war operations, the United States had provided India the modern carriers, operational aircraft, and other weapons. During exercises and activities, mutual collaboration of both the countries was significantly higher. In the backdrop of Exercise Malabar, Pakistan conducted the global naval exercise known as AMAN wherein Russia, Japan, and the United States along with other countries took part. Due to its policies favoring China and Pakistan in the Indian Ocean, Russia had established strategic and defense ties with Pakistan and expressed interest in Gwadar Port and CPEC (Tahir & Ejaz, 2020).

The US and India had shared worries about China's increasing geopolitical and geo-economic influence worldwide, which was the foundation of the US's Indo-Pacific strategy of seeking strengthened security connections among "like-minded friends" in the region and beyond. The plan for consolidating and enhancing the US network of alliances to restrict China in the Asia-Pacific region was initiated by the Trump administration. India was designated as the region's "net safety supplier" under the US policy. Throughout the two decades of NATO's presence in Afghanistan, Islamabad had continuously insisted that New Delhi was a competitor in the war which utilized Afghan territory to promote terrorism in Pakistan. In 2018, the United States granted Strategic Trade Authorization-1 (STA-1) status to India,

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making it the only South Asian state and the third Asian state overall to enjoy the said status. Modern military hardware could be sold to India under the said category without having to meet license criteria. Only close companions who participated in the four export control regimes were given STA-1 status by the US (Mehreen & Abid, 2022).

The geopolitical landscape of South Asia and the Indo-Pacific had been profoundly impacted by the strategic partnership between the United States and India. Pakistan's strategic considerations were made more difficult by increased Indo-US naval collaboration and joint exercises in the Indian Ocean, which strengthened India's military extension and protected key sea routes. Furthermore, according to experts of strategic studies, more power inequality in conventional military weapons lowered the probability of applying nuclear arms under limits, giving smaller powers fewer alternatives to secure their defenses. The same was true in the South Asian context, given India's expanding traditional military strength. Pakistan was forced to reconsider its nuclear posture and create new weaponry capabilities in order to restore regional nuclear stability when India lowered the nuclear boundary through the purchase of nuclear submarines and pinpoint strike technologies from the US. Furthermore, because there was little opportunity for a limited or completely traditional conflict in South Asia, the said development put regional and international security at risk. The growing defense collaboration between the United States and India had been speeding up the competition for conventional and nuclear weapons in South Asia. With US support, India had been strengthening its military capabilities. Pakistan felt itself bound to maintain strategic equality by strengthening its own defense capabilities. Pakistan had to bear enormous financial and resource expenses as a result of that arms race, which took its domestic funding away from important social and economic development projects. By increasing the possibility of conflict and regional insecurity, the continuous cycle of military modernization and weapons accumulation compromised efforts to create sustainable peace and security (Khan, 2024).

India and the US had become more connected as a result of the export control waiver that was provided to India. That assisted India in achieving its leadership's "Make in India" goal by boosting its regional defense businesses. The

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already-existing disparities between India and its greatest regional rival, Pakistan, had been greatly impacted by that development. India needed the newest technology to enhance the engines of its defender missiles as part of its two-layered ballistic missile defense (Kakar, 2022). Additionally, that agreement had diplomatic consequences. The US had not resolved the then-existing conflicts between India and Pakistan, including the Kashmir problem. As had frequently happened during the administrations of all recent US presidents save Obama, who completely declined to facilitate any arbitration over the conflict and insisted on resolving it on their own, the US offered to mediate the Kashmir dispute between India and Pakistan, but India consistently declined, claiming that it was their internal matter. One recent example was the multiple offers extended by US President Donald Trump to act as a mediator between India and Pakistan in order to settle the Kashmir dispute. That indicated that there won't be a resolution to the problem anytime sooner due to India's persistent refusal to engage in conversation on the basis of falsely accusing Pakistan of terrorism (Yadav, 2018).

6. Reviewing some Major Defense Agreements

Since 2014, India had also taken part in the biggest Rim of the Pacific (RIMPAC) naval operation in the world, which was led by the United States. In November 2019, the two nations held Tiger Triumph, their initial tri-service military exercise. Additionally, the US took part in the international Milan naval exercise, which was hosted by the Indian Navy, for the first time in March 2022. There was a bigger risk to regional and international security from these combined defense exercises involving all three military services. Due to India's recognition as a "major defense partner" by the US in 2016, defense trade was a significant aspect of the Indo-US strategic partnership, which had been growing after that. In 2021, the US Department of State reported that the defense trade between the US and India grew from almost \$0 in 2008 to \$20 billion in 2020. Furthermore, the two nations had signed a number of defense agreements, including the Defense Technology and Trade Initiative (DTTI) of 2012, which permitted India to work with the US to jointly develop innovative weapon systems using advanced military technology. India had been able to carry out secret intelligence gathering activities against Pakistan owing to these technologies and weapon systems. Furthermore, with US

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technological support, India had become able to obtain immediate data in the event of a crisis, particularly in the Indian Ocean Region (IOR). It is worth-recalling here about the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue (Quad), which involved the US, India, Japan, and Australia and which began as an unofficial organization in 2007 and declared its dedication to an Indo-Pacific that would be free, open, fair, secure, and wealthier. As a consequence of the Beijing's complaints, which saw the Quad plan as an Asian NATO meant only to restrict China, the plan could not make any progress in 2008. However, the Quad re-emerged in November 2017 during the 31st ASEAN Summit. The Indo-Pacific region, which accounted for 60% of maritime trade, had been the focus of the Quad. It was a vital route for world trade and energy supply. The region's geostrategic importance for the US was highlighted by the \$1.9 trillion US trade that was carried through the passage in 2019 (Mehreen & Abid, 2022).

In order to enjoy and exercise the veto power and demonstrate its position as a major world power, India also aspired to become a permanent member of the UN Security Council. As a lone regional power, it encouraged separatist elements and organized terrorism in Balochistan to destabilize Pakistan and destroy China's Belt & Road Initiative (BRI) program to threaten the economic and security interests of both these countries (Rashid, 2018). Some experts in Pakistan viewed the Indo-US strategic partnership as a potential security risk however some scholars believed that it might be beneficial and present opportunities for Pakistan as well. Nevertheless, the authorities in Pakistan felt that India's conventional and strategic capabilities were further strengthened by the provision of advanced US military technologies and logistic support through agreements like that of producing F414 engine in India and Master Ship Repair agreements, making it more difficult for Pakistan to uphold regional strategic balance and national security. Because it had to provide significant economic prospects and infrastructure investments, the CPEC was a crucial component of Pakistan's economic growth strategy. However, because of its strategic emphasis on limiting Chinese dominance in the region, the Indo-US alliance posed a direct challenge to CPEC. The improved attacking and monitoring Indian capabilities, which were further supported by US technology, compromised the security of CPEC projects. It posed a further threat to the already highly volatile regions, that were also at the heart of CPEC, such as Gilgit-Baltistan and

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Balochistan. The risk was further increased by the potential for somewhat extended Indian secret operations, aided by the transfer of the aforementioned advanced technology, aimed at damaging the CPEC and hindering Pakistan's ambitions for achieving an improved regional connectivity and economic growth (Khan, 2024).

The US previously proposed several requirements and limitations relating to the transmission of nuclear technology through nuclear testing. However, it later violated the agreement and raised the said criterion in accordance with the Nuclear Suppliers Group (NSG) regulations. The troubling thing was that although the United States had stepped back after violating the requirement, but the minor states were still in danger since India's nuclear tests could cause issues for the neighboring states particularly Pakistan. The need for Pakistan to boost its defense budget, which was already too short because of the enormous expenditures on the war on terror and the eradication of terrorist activities throughout the country, was one of the foremost outcome of India's extended nuclear and armaments development Program which was compelled to invest heavily in defense projects in order to establish a balance of power with India. The competitive rivalry in terms of arms production and development of strategic weaponry in South Asia was a result of the extraordinary US support to boost Indian defense capabilities. Uncertainty between India and Pakistan further prevailed over India's use of its nuclear capabilities for military purposes. The distinction between a nuclear power plant used for civilian purposes and one used for military purposes is extremely vague. Many observers believed that it had been extremely simple for the Indian government to convert civilian weapons to military weapons (Khan et al., 2022).

7. Overall Repercussions of US-India Cooperation

The cooperation between India and US carried a number of diplomatic and geopolitical consequences as well. Pakistan moved closer to China as a result of US estrangement from Pakistan which policy had undoubtedly worsened the already chaotic situation in South Asia. In addition to upsetting other regional states, this chaotic condition forced both Pakistan and China to involve in a web of alliances. Since the military establishment in India had remained involved in political affairs at a lesser degree as compared to Pakistan, the US viewed India as a more democratic nation than Pakistan. Furthermore, India enjoyed more shared political values with

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the US and was thus a better candidate for US partnership. Because of these realities, India continued to interfere in Pakistan's internal affairs and had fully transformed itself into a US proxy in South Asia, which fact created problems for other regional countries (Rashid, et al., 2023).

China's economy has become the world's second largest economy. There had not remained much of economic difference between the US and China. On the other hand, China, by that time, was not as technologically advanced as the United States. The US naval forces had grown more powerful since the introduction of P8I-Posedian, which used long-range aircraft to hunt for submarines. The United States had been leading P8I-Posedian to India in the Indian Ocean. U.S. had been providing carriers, vessels, stealth (large radius) submarines, aircrafts, anti-submarines, nuclear technology and nuclear aid, weapons, naval ships to India, so both countries could conduct large scale naval exercises in order to defeat the joint naval forces of China and Pakistan. The United States was giving India nuclear technology and naval assistance in the Indian Ocean because India was unable to cover the gap present in Pakistani naval capabilities which, then, were far better as compared to the Indian capacities. In addition, India's offensive naval battle forces and potential continued to grow disproportionately in comparison to Pakistan. The United States was helping India become more powerful by giving it advanced submarines and other technological support (Tahir & Ejaz, 2020).

8. Conclusion

A change in regional dynamics had been brought by the strategic alliance between the US and India, with the help of which India became able to counterbalance China's influence in the Indo-Pacific. India's closer and tighter ties to a major power like the US improved its military and economic capacities, boosting its geopolitical standing and securing its place as a major regional actor. This alliance strengthened the US's strategic position in Asia and fostered a common goal of preserving the balance of power. But for Pakistan, this collaboration presented serious difficulties. India's strategic capabilities were strengthened by US-India accords like Basic Exchange and Cooperation Agreement (BECA) and Defense Technology and Trade Initiative (DTTI), which also changed the South Asian security balance. India's previous policy of maintaining minimum deterrence had been changed as a result of

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these Indo-US strategic transitions, and Pakistan's security had consequently become an issue of serious concern. The stability of the area had been threatened since the India-US collaboration resulted in an arms race in South Asia. It also added to a security problem in which India's growing confidence was reflected in Pakistan's growing dissatisfaction.

References

- Amin, H. (2021). Security of Pakistan under the Shadow of Indo-US Strategic Partnership. *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry*, 12(8), 6502-6519.
- Amir, I. (2024). Indo-US Strategic Partnership in the 21st Century: Implications for Pakistan. *Pakistan Horizon*, 77(4), 81-94.
- Bukhari, S. S. H. (2011). India-United States Strategic Partnership: *Implications for Pakistan*. *Berkeley Journal of Social Sciences*, 1(1), 1-28.
- Iqbal, A. (2020). Indo-US Strategic Partnership and Its Fall Outs on Pakistan. *Journal of Politics and International Studies*, 6(2), 189-202.
- Jain, B. (2016). *India-US Relations in the Age of Uncertainty: An Uneasy Courtship*. New York: Routledge Taylor and Francis Group.
- Kakar, S. A. (2022). Containing China: The Indo-US Defense Cooperation. *BTTN Journal*, 1(1), 68-84.
- Khan, A. A. (2024). Indo-US Military Partnership in 2023: Examining Ramifications For Pakistan's Security In The Evolving Strategic Environment. *Centre for Aerospace and Security Studies Lahore*.
- Khan, M. K., Rafeeq, R., & Ashraf, M. I. (2022). Growing Strategic Alliance between India and USA: Implications on Pakistan. *Annals of Human and Social Sciences*, 3(2), 292-300.
- Kirk, J. A. (2008). Indian-Americans and the US-India Nuclear Agreement: Consolidation of an Ethnic Lobby? *Foreign Policy Analysis*, 4(3), 275-300
- Kumar, N. (2014). Building Grand Strategy with Indian characteristics for rebounding India. *Journal of Indian Research*, 2(1), 4-34.
- Mehreen, S., & Abid, I. (2022). Indo-US Strategic Convergence. *CISS Insight Journal*, 10(1), 49-65.
- Pant, H. V., & Super, J. M. (2015). India's 'non-alignment' conundrum: a twentieth-

Online ISSN

3007-3197

Print ISSN

3007-3189

<http://amresearchreview.com/index.php/Journal/about>

century policy in a changing world. *International Affairs*, 91(4), 747-764.

Rashid, M. I., & Javaid, U. (2018). India-US-Pakistan Strategic Relations. *Journal of the Punjab University Historical Society*, 32(1), 141-150.

Rashid, S., Majeed, G., & Ikram, M. (2023). Emerging United States-India Strategic Partnership: Implications for Pakistan. *Journal of Development and Social Sciences*, 4(3), 329-341.

Saeed, M. A., & Javaid, U. (2020). India's naval expansion and strategic partnership with the us in the Indian ocean region: implications for Pakistan. *Margalla Papers*, 24(1), 67-80.

Shahbaz, M. (2024). Indo-American Relations during Narendra Modi's Era: *A Critical Analysis*. 7(4), 1-12.

Tahir, A., & Ejaz, K. (2020). India-United States strategic partnership in Indian ocean region and its implications for Pakistan. *Journal of Indian studies*, 6(1), 7-24.

Yadav, R. S. (2018). Indo-US Relations in the Post-Cold War Era: Changing Contours. *Sage Publications*, 4(1), 3-20.